

Acceptability of Philippine English in Academic Research Communication: Challenging 'Non-Native Speakerism' In Published Research

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Abstract

Background: Several extensively documented studies have been conducted on Philippine English (PhE) as a variety of World Englishes; however, its acceptability in international publishing contexts or formal academic writing remains underexplored.

Objective: This study determines the presence and acceptability of Philippine English features in internationally published, peer-reviewed research articles authored by Filipino scholars.

Methodology: This study employed a qualitative, interpretative research design. The data collection utilised a focused content analysis approach, targeting a purposive sample of eight research articles authored by Filipino scholars. The selection criteria mandated that all articles be indexed in either the Scopus or Web of Science (WoS) databases, ensuring high scholarly rigour. The analysis involved systematic coding and thematic extraction to identify recurring patterns, concepts, and arguments within the selected publications.

Results: The systematic content analysis of research articles reveals three primary characteristics of Philippine English (PhE): (1) Localized vocabulary, where PhE exhibits a distinct lexicon that preserves cultural and social genuineness while simultaneously mediating between local and worldwide identities; (2) Lexical innovations and grammatical deviations, where the language demonstrates significant lexical innovation through the integration of native Filipino terms and systematic deviations from standard grammatical norms; and (3) distinct educational register, where PhE maintains a unique academic tone in educational settings, a feature directly attributable to the enduring historical and educational impacts on the Philippine linguistic landscape.

Conclusion: The evidence confirms the broad acceptance of Philippine English (PhE) within international scholarly discourse, thereby validating its distinctiveness and legitimacy among foreign scholars and peer reviewers. This empirical acceptance critically intensifies the claim for the endonormative stabilisation of Philippine English as a recognised variety of World Englishes.

Unique contribution: This study made a pioneering contribution by providing actual presence and editorial acceptance of Philippine English in the peer-reviewed research articles

encompassing an external acceptability in global scholarly discourse. Moreover, this study marks a significant step in dismantling the concepts of native speakerism and non-native speakerism, as well as legitimising and intensifying World Englishes.

Key Recommendation: The integration of World Englishes, specifically Philippine English, must be fully incorporated in both local and international academic writing instruction to reflect and intensify the pluricentrism of the English language and promote legitimate academic registers across the global academic settings.

Keywords: Philippine English (PhE); World Englishes (WE); Linguistic Acceptability/Norms; Content Analysis; Academic Register; Lexical Innovation; Filipino Scholars.

Introduction

Academic research communication is inherently linguistic. The way research is articulated—through written genres such as journal articles, conference papers, and dissertations—depends on language not only as a medium of transmission but also as a framework for constructing meaning, demonstrating credibility, and negotiating disciplinary identities (Hopkins, 2022). Language, therefore, is not peripheral but central to knowledge production and scholarly participation. In multilingual and postcolonial contexts, such as the Philippines, this link becomes more complex as local English varieties serve as mediators of access to global academic platforms.

Academic research communication refers to the written and verbal practices through which knowledge is created, shared, and legitimised within the scholarly community (Espino, 2021). This study focuses on its written dimension, particularly peer-reviewed journal articles, which are central to academic visibility and legitimacy. These texts are governed by rhetorical conventions, disciplinary expectations, and language ideologies that affect both access and acceptance in global publishing.

World Englishes refers to the diversity of English used globally, reflecting linguistic and cultural adaptations (Deng & Budiman, 2024). The belief in the supremacy or dominance of non-native speakerism in the English language, whether written or spoken, is definitely challenged by the recognised contributions of non-native speakers worldwide. This change or move is a significant step in promoting an inclusive approach to appreciating linguistic and cultural diversity among English speakers. Moreover, Hopkins (2022) emphasised that the complex and profound influence of non-native speakers on the development of World Englishes promotes linguistic and cultural impacts. In fact, the mainstream users of the English language are actually not native speakers; they are non-native speakers, leading to the growth and expansion of localised distinct varieties of English, such as Singlish in Singapore, Philippine English (PhE) in the Philippines, Nigerian English in Nigeria, Honglish in Hong Kong, and Thai English in Thailand. Evidently, the number of non-native English speakers has outnumbered that of native speakers, which has been increasing enormously over the past few decades.

One of the subjects of research in the field of linguistics is the proliferation of the concept of World Englishes. This indicates the promotion of multilingualism in response to pedagogical inclusivity in teaching and learning different Englishes (Rose & McKinley, 2024). One notable variety of World Englishes is Philippine English, which has been examined in recent years in terms of its acceptability (Rentillo et al., 2024) and legitimacy, encompassing its linguistic

features, sociocultural context, and implications for second language pedagogy. Unfortunately, Filipino researchers and scholars continue to struggle for academic recognition.

Although Philippine English is gaining acceptance in academic writing (Hernandez, 2023), its status remains complicated, varying across levels and degrees of acceptability in social and local contexts. Additionally, the regional acceptability of PhE (Rentillo et al., 2024) has been widely adopted by young Filipinos. However, its acceptability in foreign research journals remains unexplored. Furthermore, the differences in the acceptance of Philippine English locally and globally across all domains (including younger and older, written and spoken) and social groups have numerous instances and varying views among users of the language. Alogali (2018) pointed out that Filipino scholars continue to fight for the acceptability of Philippine English in the international setting, more specifically in submitting research articles in internationally recognised journals.

Evidently, PhE acceptance in domestic academic content is tremendously increasing, but its visibility and acceptability in international scholarly journals are less explored. Although several studies have documented the lexical and grammatical features of PhE (Hernandez, 2023), there is limited research exploring its actual acceptability in internationally published academic texts, primarily peer-reviewed journal articles. Most scholarship remains focused on internal descriptions or sociolinguistic attitudes within the Philippines, leaving a gap in understanding how PhE is negotiated in global scholarly discourse.

Unlike previous studies, this study makes a unique and pioneering contribution by providing actual presence and editorial acceptance of Philippine English in peer-reviewed research articles, encompassing external acceptability in global scholarly discourse. Moreover, this study marks a significant step in dismantling the concepts of native speakerism and non-native speakerism, as well as legitimising and intensifying World Englishes, specifically Philippine English.

While existing studies have documented the grammatical and lexical features of Philippine English (e.g., Bautista, 2023; Hernandez, 2023) and examined attitudes towards its use in local domains (Rentillo et al., 2024), there is limited research on how these features are received, tolerated, or legitimised by editors and peer reviewers in international academic publishing. This gap is particularly significant in light of growing recognition of World Englishes and the continued dominance of native-speaker norms in scholarly communication.

The objective of the study is to determine the presence and editorial acceptability of Philippine English features—lexical, grammatical, and rhetorical—in internationally published, peer-reviewed research articles authored by Filipino scholars. It also seeks to explore how such features are negotiated within global academic publishing and what their inclusion signifies for the legitimacy of non-native English varieties in scholarly discourse.

Literature Review

Linguistic Features and Academic Writing

With the growing body of research documented regarding Philippine English (Rentillo et al., 2024), it continues to develop and evolve into a legitimate academic variety, exhibiting distinct grammatical and rhetorical features that are consistently observed in scholarly writing.

Hernandez (2023) observed one such feature, which is the use of specific subject-verb agreement patterns that appear across research articles in various disciplines, suggesting the internal stability and functional legitimacy of these constructions within the academic register. This implies a shift from a peripheral status to an emerging, codified, and classified variety of the English language.

Paz (2022) revealed that research abstracts found in Philippine e-journals tend to favour specific rhetorical patterns and language choices. This includes the use of the simple past tense and active voice, creating a more transparent and coherent text for readers to follow. This reflects the preservation of PhE's distinct character and exhibits how it regulates the standards or expectations of formal academic writing. This kind of stylistic tendency highlights the enormous ability of Philippine English to align with international communication norms. That said, most existing studies focus more on describing these features than on exploring how they are perceived or negotiated in international academic settings—something this study seeks to examine more closely.

Acceptability and Attitude Towards Philippine English

Generational, contextual, and domain-specific variables shape the sociolinguistic acceptability of PhE. Rentillo et al. (2024) found that younger Filipinos exhibit greater acceptance of PhE, particularly in educational and professional domains, suggesting a positive shift in local language ideology. However, this acceptance is less stable in online spaces, where prescriptive norms and the native-speaker model continue to dominate debates about “correctness” (Paz, 2022).

These conflicting attitudes reveal a tension between linguistic authenticity and standard language ideology, with significant implications for PhE's inclusion in formal domains. Yet, current scholarship rarely explores how acceptability is operationalised in published academic discourse, particularly by international editors or reviewers. This study thus addresses a critical gap: the extent to which linguistic features of PhE are actually visible and permitted in globally indexed publications.

Lexical Features and Grammatical Features

Philippine English's lexical identity is shaped by both historical contact and creative innovation. The continued use of Spanish loanwords, such as *población* or *sala*, highlights the enduring influence of colonial history on the Filipino lexicon (Biermeier, 2022). Simultaneously, local word-formation processes—such as clipping, compounding, and analogical extension—demonstrate an active nativisation of English vocabulary.

These lexical adaptations are not merely pragmatic; they are ideologically significant. This reflects the localised reengineering of different English terms to express Filipino genuineness and realities that challenge any lexical legitimacy. It is evident in most compound nouns written in Philippine English that are less common in spoken registers, indicating formal and stylistic directions modelled by different genres.

The linguistic deviations of PhE are uniformly remarkable. Recurring patterns include non-standard subject-verb agreement, especially involving collective nouns, missing articles, and prepositional variation (Cavanlit, 2022). While such features may appear as “errors” under

traditional norms, they, in fact, represent emerging internal regularities within PhE. For instance, unique tense-aspect combinations suggest a developing grammar distinct from British or American English.

PhE is also regionally and socially variable, adapting to context-specific communicative needs. This fluidity is evident in media discourse, legal texts (e.g., police blotters), and social media usage (Servano, 2024). Moreover, intonational and syntactic innovations, such as exclamative constructions, set PhE apart from other World Englishes. These features underscore PhE's linguistic plurality and contextual adaptability. However, few studies have explored how these features are treated in global academic publishing—whether tolerated, revised, or accepted outright—leaving a critical gap in understanding the gatekeeping of English in scholarly communication.

The reviewed literature affirms that PhE is not a deficient version of English but a developing, systematised variety grounded in Philippine sociocultural contexts. However, much of the research remains descriptive. There is limited inquiry into how these linguistic features function within the politics of academic gatekeeping, especially in relation to international journals. This study builds on this body of work by shifting the focus from the internal features of PhE to its external acceptability: how, when, and why PhE features are allowed to appear in peer-reviewed publications. In doing so, it contributes to broader theoretical debates in World Englishes and language ideology, especially concerning endonormative stabilisation and the global legitimisation of non-native varieties.

Methodology

This research study employed a qualitative approach, specifically focusing on written documents to understand and analyse meanings within and through texts. This approach employs several common strategies, including in-depth interviews, participant observation, and content analysis. Documents are thoroughly examined and observed. In connection, the researcher utilised qualitative content analysis, structuring and analysing the textual content of published research articles to gain a comprehensive understanding of the content in terms of the features of Philippine English.

Eight peer-reviewed, open-access research articles were selected between 2021 and 2024. The following are the criteria for selecting articles: authored by Filipino researchers, published in Scopus- or WoS-indexed journals, and with a topic in linguistics, education, or sociolinguistics, accessible via databases such as Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, PubMed, and Mendeley. The selection was guided by purposive sampling, aiming to capture academic work likely to feature localised English usage. The following are the selected research articles: (Eslit, 2023); (Dimaculangan, 2022); (Espino et al., 2021); (Bautista & Valle, 2023); (Gamad et al., 2023); (Quimosing-Ocay & Ocampo, 2024); (Rada, 2022); and (Lavadia, 2023). Documents that met the criteria were downloaded and, therefore, included in the pool of articles for consideration and analysis. The different sections of the journal articles were considered and subjected to content analysis.

Content analysis, specifically the Directed Qualitative Content Analysis (DQCA), was conducted in three stages. First, textual scanning involved comprehensive readings of each article to identify potential Philippine English features, such as localised vocabulary, syntactic

patterns, and rhetorical tone. Second, in the coding and categorisation stage, the identified features were organised using a deductive-inductive coding process, drawing on established frameworks in World Englishes research. Features were classified into three main categories: lexical (e.g., loanwords, neologisms, localised terms), grammatical (e.g., tense-aspect variation, article and preposition usage, subject-verb agreement patterns), and rhetorical (e.g., tone, textual transitions, and academic register), in the last stage, which is the interpretation phase, the different patterns were analysed in terms of their function, frequency, and implications of PhE terms or expressions perceived in international academic publishing. The coding process was independently reviewed by experts with knowledge and training in World Englishes, specifically Philippine English, to ensure the reliability of the results. The evaluation of this study was conducted by the university's Research Ethics Committee (REC), which ensures consideration of its ethical implications and the implementation of the study.

Results And Discussion

Presence and Editorial Acceptability of Philippine English in Published Research

Localised Filipino Vocabulary

The use of untranslatable Filipino words in academic research articles—such as *barangay* (refers to a village or community unit), *aswang* (a mythical creature in Philippine folklore), *sarimanok* (a bird symbolising good fortune in Maranao culture), *babaylan* (pre-colonial spiritual leader and shaman), and *tiyanak* (a mythological creature, demonic baby)—signals a deliberate linguistic strategy: to assert cultural authenticity while engaging with global scholarly standards. These terms signal a deliberate linguistic strategy, asserting cultural authenticity while engaging with global scholarly standards. These terms, often without direct English equivalents, are inserted without quotation marks or glosses, suggesting that authors presume either familiarity or contextual intelligibility. This challenges traditional norms of standard English, where non-Anglophone terms are often footnoted or italicised.

The usage of Filipino vocabulary in research articles aligns with Paz's (2022) notion of “cultural keywords,” which serve not only communicative but also ideological purposes. Their inclusion without resistance from reviewers indicates a form of discursive accommodation—a tacit acceptance of localised identity markers in global academic writing. Rather than being constrained by native-speaker norms, these articles exemplify how PhE negotiates legitimacy through lexical hybridity. However, more evidence is needed to determine whether this tolerance reflects a stable norm or a case-by-case editorial discretion. The above-mentioned Filipino concepts or terms in Philippine English, as applied in the published articles, demonstrate the preservation of culture among Filipinos, even with the use of the English language. Mostly, these words cannot be directly translated into English, as they carry deep connotations rooted in Filipino traditions, history, beliefs, and norms. This is an indication of the hybrid nature of Philippine English, which exists alongside cultural authenticity, international intelligibility, and assimilation.

Furthermore, some Filipino words have been acculturated by English loanwords, exhibiting Philippine grammatical features and harmonising morphological adaptations. With this kind of process or transformation, semantic shifts and phonological rules are significantly modified, denoting a rapid linguistic reciprocity that incorporates cultural components (Sulit et al., 2024). Additionally, a notable recognition was made by including Philippine English terms in the Oxford Dictionary, which implies its genuine linguistic and cultural perspectives, for instance,

sari-sari store (a small, convenient neighbourhood store selling various goods) and suki (a buyer or seller who is loyal to purchasing specific brands or goods). This global recognition of Filipino vocabulary encourages the acceptance of its use and integration in academic and professional writing and perspectives.

The preservation of Filipino vocabulary or keywords promotes a linguistic pathway between international recognition and local identification, which applies the sociolinguistic and cultural pattern of Philippine English. As accepted in published research articles, the identified Filipino words indicate that PhE provides distinct aspects of Filipino heritage or culture, even though it is immersed in the global community through academic writing in research publications. However, with the acceptance, it reflects the complete portrayal of the differences in Filipino cultural concepts, hence embracing these Filipino native terms by peer reviewers or editors who are not familiar with the Philippine English words.

Lexical Innovations and Grammatical Deviation

The emergence of Philippine English as a variety of World Englishes displays unique lexical innovation (terminological language evolution) and grammatical deviation (non-standard language use). Lexical innovation is a concept in linguistics that involves creating and introducing new words or expressions within a particular language, taking into account cultural evolution and linguistic creativity. This demonstrates that lexical innovations in PhE reflect the dynamic evolution of the language as it adapts to local contexts and gains worldwide significance. On the other hand, grammatical deviation is the diversion of established grammatical rules of a specific language.

In the identified published research articles, the following words/phrases were identified: *with regards*, *presidentiable*, *academician*, *cope up with*, *wrong grammar*, and *one of the teachers is*. This confirms the study by Cavanlit (2022), which solidified the concept of Philippine English in relation to lexical innovations in academic writing and its grammatical structure. These were reported to be acceptable among users of the language. In contrast to Rentillo et al. (2024), who focused on local acceptability, this study reveals international editorial tolerance of such lexical innovations, extending their argument into the global publishing context. Moreover, common phrasal-prepositional verbs in PhE include "come up with," "get out of," "look forward to," and "catch up with," which are idiomatic and used conservatively. These terms are not arbitrary; they reflect culturally embedded concepts that lack direct equivalents in other Englishes. For instance, *presidentiable* encapsulates a political category widely understood in the Philippine context despite its nonexistence in standard American or British English dictionaries.

In the reviewed articles, these terms are presented without caveats or quotation marks, suggesting that the authors—and presumably the peer reviewers—regard them as functionally legitimate within scholarly discourse. This unmarked usage contrasts with earlier norms that treated such items as errors or colloquialisms, implying a shift in perceived linguistic legitimacy. Moreover, the recurrence of these innovations across different texts suggests they are not isolated anomalies but part of an emerging academic lexicon.

In tandem with lexical creativity, the data also show grammatical deviations that typify PhE usage. Patterns such as "one of the teachers is," "cope up with," and variable subject-verb

agreement—particularly in constructions with intervening prepositional phrases—recur in the corpus. According to Cavanlit (2022), such forms reflect internal regularities that are contextually and grammatically consistent within PhE, even if they diverge from Inner Circle norms. These deviations should not be framed as errors but rather as indicators of endonormative restructuring, wherein a postcolonial variety begins to stabilise its own norms independently of external (native-speaker) models.

Interestingly, none of the research articles in question flagged these deviations through parenthetical explanations or self-corrections. This suggests a degree of editorial tolerance or oversight—either the features went unnoticed, or they were deemed acceptable within the broader goal of disseminating knowledge rather than policing form. In either case, this points to a gradual loosening of normative boundaries in academic publishing.

While some scholars may interpret these deviations as indicators of a still-developing or non-standard variety, this study adopts a World Englishes perspective: such features are not linguistic deficits but rather signs of PhE’s functional expansion and contextual appropriateness. However, the absence of metadata on reviewer comments or editorial revisions limits our ability to conclusively determine whether these features were consciously accepted or inadvertently overlooked—a limitation that future research must address.

English has significantly influenced Filipinos through the borrowing of lexemes, which undergo morphophonological adaptations to fit the phonological and grammatical structures of Filipinos. This process involves inflexions with Filipino morphemes and modifications to phonological rules, resulting in semantic shifts and changes in the morphophonological structure of phrases and sentences (Sulit et al., 2024). Also, in academic writing, Philippine English exhibits unique subject-verb agreement patterns, such as the consistent use of intervening prepositional phrases under verb-related agreement. In this kind of pattern, although prevalent and organised, recommending it for usability in Philippine English is definitely an acceptable grammatical innovation.

Distinct Educational Register

In addition to lexical and grammatical features, the selected articles consistently employed a distinct educational register, shaped by the Philippine sociocultural and institutional context. Terms such as *Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE)*, *K-12 Program*, *Program Educational Objectives*, and *master's* reflect not only localised nomenclature but also context-bound conceptual frameworks that are integral to Philippine educational discourse. These expressions, while potentially unfamiliar to global audiences, were presented in the articles without definition or justification, suggesting an assumed legitimacy and intelligibility within international publishing contexts.

For instance, *master's*, a term commonly used in Philippine academic settings (Tupas, 2024) to refer to postgraduate degrees, has no direct counterpart in standard British or American English, where “master’s” is the preferred form. Its unmarked usage in peer-reviewed publications implies either editorial acceptance or strategic authorial positioning that normalises localised academic terminology. Similarly, MTB-MLE and the K-12 Program are not merely technical labels; they encapsulate national education reforms and pedagogical philosophies that are uniquely suited to the Philippine context. Their inclusion in academic

articles signals the assertion of epistemic sovereignty—that is, the authority to name and frame educational practices based on local realities.

These findings suggest that PhE is not only tolerated but also used as a medium for articulating indigenous academic concepts. The presence of such terms reinforces the idea that language in academic writing is not purely about form but also about representation and legitimacy. While the global reception of these localised terms remains uncertain, their appearance in indexed journals indicates a possible redefinition of what constitutes “standard” academic English. However, this trend raises important questions: Are these terms universally understood and accepted, or are they overlooked due to the focus on content over linguistic form? Do they enhance or hinder global intelligibility? These unresolved issues underscore the need for further inquiry into how localised educational discourse travels and is received in transnational academic spaces.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This research investigated the acceptability of Philippine English by looking into the presence of its features in internationally published research articles authored by Filipino scholars. By utilising qualitative content analysis, eight peer-reviewed research articles were selected, and recurring lexical innovations, grammatical patterns, and culturally embedded vocabulary characteristic of PhE were identified. Rather than being marked as errors or inconsistencies, these features appeared unflagged and contextually appropriate, suggesting a degree of editorial accommodation and a potential shift in academic gatekeeping practices towards greater linguistic inclusivity.

The findings provide empirical support for the ongoing endonormative stabilisation of PhE—an important stage in the evolution of World Englishes, where a variety begins to codify and assert its own norms independently. Specifically, the inclusion of culturally specific terms (e.g., *barangay*, *sari-sari store*), context-driven grammatical patterns (e.g., unique subject–verb agreement constructions), and local academic terminology (e.g., *presidentiable*, *masteral*) reflect how PhE is being negotiated—and to some extent, accepted—within global scholarly discourse.

The current study provides a validated indication that Philippine English is a discernible and distinguishable variety of English, shaped by cultural and linguistic influences. The research explored the acceptability of PhE in prescribed research articles. The study's results highlight the integration of Filipino vocabulary in published articles, underscoring the hybrid nature of PhE, where untranslatable cultural concepts are preserved to maintain cultural identity, as accepted by international journals. This is an excellent manifestation of Philippine English's accurate representation in academic writing and professional settings.

Moreover, it is indicative that foreign peer reviewers are accepting the identified features of Philippine English in the published research articles. Amidst the debate on World Englishes and Philippine English, this milestone marks a significant advancement in the research and education of its distinctiveness, legitimacy, and validity among scholars and researchers. Additionally, the findings of this study provide further evidence for the ongoing debate on the endonormative stabilisation of PhE. It definitely implies strong evidence that PhE is being

accepted both locally and globally, as evidenced by the stabilisation of new varieties and codification.

A key strength of this study is its use of actual published articles, which allows for an authentic observation of editorial and peer-review practices concerning Philippine English. This empirical approach contributes novel insights into the global legitimisation of non-native English varieties. However, this research's limited sample size of eight articles, the focus only on Filipino-authored articles, and the lack of direct insights or understanding from peer reviewers or editors are some constraints in the findings' generalisability. Moreover, precise knowledge of the utilisation of PhE in research articles can be gained if there is access to draft versions or reviewer feedback to verify whether the identified PhE features were overlooked or intentionally encouraged. Future studies may conduct triangulation of the text or content analysis with interviews or surveys among journal editors, peer reviewers, and authors to better understand the procedures or mechanisms involved in accepting linguistic features of PhE in academic writing and publishing.

Future studies should explore how peer reviewers and editors perceive and evaluate the inclusion of non-native English features, especially Philippine English, in academic manuscripts. This could involve qualitative interviews with journal gatekeepers, surveys of international publishing practices, or comparative analyses across journals with different impact factors. Longitudinal studies could also examine whether the editorial tolerance of PhE features increases over time as World Englishes gain more prominence in academia.

In the pedagogical and academic approach, the results and findings indicated in this study support a more comprehensive understanding of Philippine English taught in English language instruction in the Philippines, emphasising its valid and legitimate academic register. Utilising localised features of Philippine English for both basic education and higher education may definitely alleviate students' confidence in their linguistic identity and scholarly writing on the global scene more effectively and efficiently.

In the same vein, this study significantly contributes to the growing global recognition of Philippine English as a linguistically diverse and contextually relevant variety of English that deserves not only local affirmation but also international academic legitimacy. PhE's features, moulded and shaped by identified culture and creative adaptation, characterise how English continues to evolve in dynamic, vigorous, and pluricentric ways worldwide.

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